

A STUDY ON THE EMPLOYMENT ABILITY AND IMPROVEMENT PATH OF COLLEGE STUDENTS IN JIANGXI PROVINCE

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Abstract

In recent years, in the process of rapid popularization of higher education in China, the issue of employment for college students has become increasingly prominent, and has also received high attention from society. After investigation, it was found that college graduates are increasing day by day, but their comprehensive quality, employment ability, and other aspects are uneven, and there is a large gap with the actual needs of employers, which restricts the smooth employment of the majority of graduates. Therefore, this article takes college students in Jiangxi Province as the research object, starting from employment ability and enterprise demand, and uses structural equation modeling to study the mechanism of enterprise demand on employment ability. Through research, it is found that employment ability and enterprise demand are significantly positively correlated, and enterprise demand has a positive effect on college students' employment ability.

1. BACKGROUND

In recent years, due to the enrollment expansion policy, the number of college graduates in China is also on the rise year by year. According to the statistics of the Ministry of Education of China, the number of college graduates at all levels in 2022 will reach 10.76 million, with a net increase of 1.67 million over 2021. Due to the impact of the global epidemic from 2020 to 2022, nearly 460,000 Chinese enterprises will close down in 2020, and many of them will cut off the tail to survive, laying off a large number of employees and reducing the number of college enrollments. In addition to the unemployed graduates over the years, enterprises and other employers will have higher and higher requirements for college students' education and graduation from colleges. As a result, the employment difficulties of college graduates have once again become the focus of social attention. Jiangxi Province is not at the forefront level of economic development, the leadership of Jiangxi Province is also issued a letter that the need to play the province's strength, to solve the problem of difficult employment, in which the 2023 session of college graduates in Jiangxi Province is expected to reach 457,000 people, an increase of 83,000 people than in 2022, how to crack the problem of employment of graduates of colleges and universities, how to further improve the quality of the students, and how to further build the high level of college education institutions faculty is an urgent problem to be solved.

Most enterprises also say that there are a lot of job vacancies, mainly because of the mismatch of talents, and the talents that enterprises need are mainly from college students. Colleges and universities also play an intermediary role between enterprises and college students, especially the support of colleges and universities and the participation of students in social practice. It

can also be said that the most important ability is reflected in the employment level. The employability of college students is reflected by the job they find, their satisfaction with the job, and the degree of matching with their major.

Therefore, it is more important for enterprises to match their employability with their needs. Under the support and guidance of national policies, pilot colleges and universities at the undergraduate level are also actively conducting innovation and reform, cultivating application-oriented talents and cultivating the main force of the future society. As an enterprise, how to attract talent to meet the needs of sustainable development is also a long-term and in-depth problem that enterprises need to think about in the future. If the employability of college students can be matched from the perspective of the talent demand of enterprises, it can further provide a reference for college students to improve their employability.

To sum up, this paper will build an evaluation system in line with college students' employability from the four special abilities of college students' employability: professional ability, interpersonal ability, self-development ability, and emotional regulation ability, and then further design the questionnaire accordingly.

2. OPERATIONAL DEFINITION

2.1 Enterprise demand

With the continuous improvement of the market economy, the employment needs of enterprises are more market-oriented, enterprises have their own principles of employment, but in general, they choose high-quality talents according to the development of their own enterprises. Through studying the relevant literature, this paper believes that the most important thing for enterprises to recruit college graduates is teamwork, professional knowledge, communication ability, and resistance to frustration and pressure.

(1) Teamwork

Teamwork refers to the ability of all members of a team to complete team tasks with high quality and efficiency through teamwork and teamwork. With the advent of the digital age, digital technology is changing the nature and mode of teamwork, and teamwork plays an important role in the completion of projects (Larson & DeChurch. (2020); Aaron Schechter et al. (2023); Allert et al. (2021)). It is not only university students who need teamwork skills, but also teachers within educational institutions who need to be able to work well in teams, especially in terms of exchange of learning between colleagues in terms of instructional improvement, team improvement, and school improvement for further development (Wullschleger et al. (2023)).

(2) Expertise

Expertise is a multi-faceted and multi-dimensional concept, which not only includes a deep understanding of the professional knowledge learned but also includes a proficient grasp of relevant skills and methods. Mastery of professional knowledge can be demonstrated in

many ways, such as exam results, practical ability, work experience, academic research, and so on. Understanding how expertise is developed and maintained is an interesting issue in many different professional fields, and even more so, it is believed that the positive qualities of an expert, such as proficiency, experience, knowledge, keen insight, and ease of getting along, the better they perform at work, and the more they reflect superiority in their position, and thus expertise mastery plays an important role in employment, among other things (Ward et al. (2018); Joss Berger et al. (2022); Boshuizen et al. (2020)).

(3) Communication

People are people in society, and they cannot exist independently from society. In the information age with more developed communication technology, people are more closely connected and interact with each other, which puts forward higher requirements for people's communication ability. Good communication is at the heart of effective social work, which also contributes to the development of constructive working relationships, which can moreover further improve the outcomes of social work services (Kam (2020); Tanner (2020); Healy (2017)).

(4) Resistance to stress and frustration

The degree of anti-frustration and anti-pressure can be understood as the ability to psychological confrontation in the face of frustration, which is one of the basic qualities of human psychological activities. The earliest research on the ability to resist frustration and pressure is influenced by the theory of "frustration tolerance". According to this theory, "the ability to resist setbacks is the ability of individuals to resist setbacks without adverse reactions, that is, the ability of individuals to avoid behavior disorders after setbacks." Some scholars have pointed out that highly specialized jobs require staff to have a strong resistance to frustration and stress, for example, in the case of COVID-19 the resistance to frustration and stress of first aid workers is particularly important, not only for first aid workers but also for teacher workers, etc. (Osadchyi et al. (2020)).

2.2 Employability

College students' employability refers to the ability of college students to find jobs and make work progress, which is cultivated in the process of learning and practice. This ability has an obvious career orientation and is the performance of internalizing professional knowledge, skills, and comprehensive quality. College students' employability is a collection of various career-related abilities. This paper holds that college students' employability mainly includes four ability dimensions: professional ability, interpersonal ability, self-development ability, and emotional regulation ability.

(1) Professional competence

In today's increasingly detailed social division of labor, each occupation needs a certain special ability to be competent. The college graduates studied in this paper mainly send professional talents to society, and these professional talents have special professional knowledge and skills, so they are irreplaceable. In the era of the knowledge economy,

employers pay more and more attention to whether college graduates can possess knowledge and skills commensurate with their academic qualifications. At present, some colleges and universities have the problem of “emphasizing theory over practice, knowledge over skills”. The law of the wooden bucket expresses that how much water a bucket can hold depends on its shortest board. There are also numerous studies that include professional competence, such as professional competence being more prominent in the face of major events (Christensen & Lægheid (2020); Heinonen & Nissen-Lie (2020)), which found that professional skills encompass aspects of an individual’s worldview, spirituality, sociability, and initiative and that it takes a great deal of study and practice to further enhance an individual’s employability (Hosiyatovich et al. (2023); Galiana et al. (2022); Khasanov et al. (2022)).

(2) Interpersonal skills

Interpersonal ability refers to the ability to deal with and manage the relationship with others and the influence of others on oneself, mainly including Communication skills, interpersonal communication skills, Teamwork skills, the ability to influence others, the ability to develop others, conflict management skills, leadership, the ability to drive change, etc. Many studies have concluded that interpersonal communication skills play an important role in employment, especially in positions that need to communicate with people, such as sales, teachers, and other workers. If the nature of the job requires negotiation, interpersonal communication skills are more necessary. Some scholars also believe that interpersonal skills (Lucas et al. (2023); Anderson et al. (2020)).

(3) Self-development planning

Self-development ability is the ability of individuals to continuously develop themselves according to their personal goals and the requirements of the organization and work. The ability to self-development also determines the adaptability of college students to the external environment. From the perspective of teachers’ creative ability, some scholars have proposed that developing the relationship between students’ knowledge, skills and technology can also improve the quality of college education and ultimately enhance the innovative ability of college students (Ilhamovna (2023); Nasution et al. (2023)). Summarizing and concluding the self-development ability through existing studies mainly includes 1. The ability to learn; Ability to analyze and solve problems (Sirozhiddinova (2019); Rasulovna (2021); Abilmazhinova et al. (2021)).

(4) Emotional adjustment ability

Emotion regulation refers to “the social ability to perceive the feelings and emotions of oneself and others and use them to guide one’s thinking and behavior.” Emotion is an integral part of people’s life and mental health. Studies have shown that appropriate emotion regulation plays a very important role in personal development and well-being. If an individual does not have good emotion regulation ability, his development may be limited. Some studies investigated college students’ emotional regulation ability based on real-life scenarios and involved the interaction of individual emotional regulation to promote personality support. The social ability to perceive the feelings and emotions of one’s own and others and use

them to guide one's thinking and behavior (Zhu et al. (2023); Vanderlind et al. (2020)). Emotional adjustment ability include: 1.Social cognition ability. 2.The ability to recognize oneself. 3.Self-management ability, etc (Cuevas López et al. (2021); Zehra & Yerin Guneri (2023)).

3. RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

Based on the research question, objective and variable setting, this paper hypothesized the relationship between enterprise demand and employability. The hypothesis of this paper is as follows:

H: Enterprise demand has a significant positive impact on employability.

4. QUESTIONNAIRE INVESTIGATION

Formal research was carried out on the basis of pre-research. The method of questionnaire survey was used to obtain data, and the form of questionnaire distributed was mainly the questionnaire star electronic questionnaire. The main research objects are generally graduating college students and their business managers. The sampling method in this study is non-probability sampling, that is, the combination of online and offline. Based on my own relationship, I send the questionnaire link to my relatives, friends and classmates with the help of WeChat, QQ and other tools, and ask them to forward the link to user groups of different types and regions, so as to make the sample data as representative as possible. During the formal investigation, a total of 372 questionnaires were distributed and 298 questionnaires were collected, with a recovery rate of 80.11%.

5. DATA ANALYSIS

5.1 Scale Tests

In this study, the scales related to employability and enterprise demand adopt mature scales at home and abroad, which have been verified by many scholars, but the sample results are quite different from the previous survey results.

5.1.1 Reliability Analysis

The results of the survey on employability and enterprise demand were tested for reliability, and the results are shown below.

Through the analysis results in Table 5-1 below, it can be found that the overall reliability coefficient of the total employability scale in this study is 0.976, indicating that the scale has high credibility. The reliability coefficient values of each dimension are 0.912, 0.935, 0.921 and 0.930 respectively, which are all greater than 0.8, indicating that the measurement of each variable has good reliability. It has a relatively ideal internal consistency, and the measurement indicators used in this study have high reliability. In addition, the total correlation data of each item type correction item in the employability scale are between 0.69 and 0.89, and deleting any item type cannot improve the reliability coefficient value of employability.

Table 5-1: Reliability analysis of employability

Dimensions and Measurement Question Types		Correction line total correlation	Deleted alpha coefficients for item	Subscale Cronbach alpha	Summary table Cronbach alpha
Professional competence	P1	0.694	0.976	0.912	0.976
	P2	0.721	0.975		
	P3	0.739	0.975		
	P4	0.742	0.975		
	P5	0.832	0.974		
Interpersonal skills	P6	0.847	0.974	0.935	
	P7	0.851	0.974		
	P8	0.878	0.974		
	P9	0.796	0.975		
	P10	0.773	0.975		
Self-development planning	P11	0.816	0.974	0.921	
	P12	0.822	0.974		
	P13	0.876	0.974		
	P14	0.836	0.974		
	P15	0.769	0.975		
Emotional Adjustment ability	P16	0.835	0.974	0.930	
	P17	0.849	0.974		
	P18	0.802	0.975		
	P19	0.827	0.974		
	P20	0.852	0.974		

Through the analysis results in Table 5-2 below, it can be found that the overall reliability coefficient of the total enterprise demand scale in this study is 0.969, indicating that the scale has high credibility. The reliability coefficient values of each dimension are 0.900, 0.967, 0.813 and 0.910 respectively, which are all greater than 0.8, indicating that the measurement of each variable has good reliability. It has a relatively ideal internal consistency, and the measurement indicators used in this study have high reliability. In addition, according to the total correlation data of each item type correction item in the enterprise demand scale, deleting any item type cannot improve the reliability coefficient value of enterprise demand.

Table 5-2: Reliability analysis of enterprise demand

Dimensions and Measurement Question Types		Correction line total correlation	Deleted alpha coefficients for item	Subscale Cronbach alpha	Summary table Cronbach alpha
Teamwork	I1	0.725	0.890	0.900	0.969
	I2	0.780	0.870		
	I3	0.810	0.859		
	I4	0.801	0.863		
Communication	I5	0.904	0.959	0.967	
	I6	0.931	0.955		
	I7	0.909	0.959		
	I8	0.912	0.958		
	I9	0.871	0.965		
Expertise	I10	0.610	0.777	0.813	
	I11	0.786	0.691		
	I12	0.781	0.697		
	I13	0.416	0.880		
Resistance to stress and frustration	I14	0.814	0.877	0.910	
	I15	0.793	0.884		
	I16	0.819	0.875		
	I17	0.758	0.896		

5.1.2 Validity Analysis

The so-called validity means that it can be used to measure the effectiveness of the scale, that is, the accuracy of the scale data. Content validity and construct validity are usually selected for testing in formal investigations. Content validity was used to test whether the content of the scale was appropriate, while construct validity was used to measure the consistency between the variable concept and the items measured by the variable scale.

(1) Content validity analysis

At the beginning of the questionnaire preparation, this study sorted out the relevant literature at home and abroad on exploring employability, enterprise needs, school support and social practice participation, and evaluated whether the items were consistent with the actual situation of the respondents one by one before the initial test.

(2) Construct validity analysis

This paper uses factor analysis to analyze the construct validity. Generally, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) value is between 0 and 1, and if KMO is greater than 0.7, the validity is good. If Sig is less than 0.05, the validity result is considered ideal.

Table 5-3: Employability KMO and Bartlett's overall validity test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin	Breadth	0.968
Bartlett Sphericity Test	Approximate Chi-square	11595.406
	DF	190
	P-value	0.000

Table 5-3 above shows the validity analysis and test of the data of the employability scale, and it can be obtained that the KMO value of the questionnaire is 0.968, and the P value of the test is 0.000, indicating that the questionnaire structure validity of the employability scale is good.

Table 5-4: Enterprise demand KMO and Bartlett's overall validity test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin	Breadth	0.927
Bartlett Sphericity Test	Approximate Chi-square	1272.83
	DF	136
	P-value	0.000

Table 5-4 above shows the validity analysis and test of the data of the enterprise demand scale, and it can be obtained that the KMO value of the questionnaire is 0.927, and the P value of the test is 0.000, indicating that the questionnaire structure validity of the enterprise demand scale is good.

At the same time, according to the previous research, the closer the χ^2/DF value is to 1, the better the fitting degree of the model is, less than 2 is the ideal state, more than 1 and less than 3 is acceptable; The RMSEA value is less than 0.05, indicating that the model fits very well; if the value is greater than 0.05 and less than 0.08, the model fits well; if the value is greater than 0.08 and less than 0.1, the model is acceptable. GFI, AGFI, IFI, NFI, and CFI are between 0 and 1, with higher values indicating better fitting of the model.

Table 5-5: Results of structural validity analysis of the employability questionnaire

χ^2/DF	RMSEA	GFI	AGFI	CFI	NFI	IFI
2.574	0.012	0.917	0.906	0.893	0.951	0.893

It can be seen from Table 5-5 above that the χ^2/DF value of the questionnaire is 2.574, between 1 and 3; the value of RMSEA is less than 0.1; the values of GFI, AGFI and IFI are all greater than 0.9; and the values of NFI and CFI are close to 0.9. Therefore, it also indicates that the employability scale has good structural validity.

Table 5-6: Results of the structural validity analysis of the enterprise demand questionnaire

χ^2/DF	RMSEA	GFI	AGFI	CFI	NFI	IFI
1.004	0.113	0.935	0.942	0.913	0.942	0.914

It can be seen from Table 5-6 above that the value of χ^2/df of the questionnaire is 1.004, which is between 1 and 3; the value of RMSEA is less than 0.12; and the values of GFI, AGFI, NFI, CFI and IFI are all greater than 0.9. Therefore, it also indicates that the enterprise

demand scale has good structural validity.

5.2 Relevance Analysis

Correlation analysis is a statistical analysis method to study the correlation between two or more random variables that are in the same position. Therefore, before the comprehensive exploration of the relationship among the variables, the relevant analysis of employability and enterprise demand is carried out.

Table 5-7: Correlation results of each variable

Variable Names	Employability	Enterprise demand
Employability	1.000	
Enterprise demand	0.925***	1.000

Table 5-7 above shows the correlation coefficients between employability and enterprise demand, there is a significant positive correlation between the two variables, and the hypothesis proposed earlier has been preliminarily confirmed.

5.3 Analysis of Structural Equation Model (SEM) Results

The so-called structural equation model analysis refers to the analysis by constructing the structural model between observed variables and latent variables.

Figure 5-1: Analysis model of the impact of enterprise demand on employability

Table 5-8: Analysis of the impact of enterprise demand on employability Model fit analysis

Statistical test value	RMSEA	GFI	IFI	TLI	CFI
Critical value	<0.08	>0.90	>0.90	>0.90	>0.90
Test result data	0.021	0.979	0.919	0.881	0.919
Model fit judgment	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

From Table 5-8 above, it can be seen that RMSEA is 0.021, less than 0.08; GFI is 0.979; IFI is 0.919; CFI is 0.919, all greater than 0.9; and TLI is 0.881.

In the output results of the analysis model of the impact of enterprise demand on employability, the path standardized estimate, non-standardized estimate, S.E., C.R. And significance probability values P are shown in Tables 5-9 below.

Table 5-9: Analysis of the impact of enterprise demand on employability Statistical results of path analysis

	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P-Value	Standardization Estimate
Employability<--- Enterprise demand	0.840	0.036	23.381	***	1.004
Resistance to stress and frustration<--- Enterprise demand	1.000				0.847
Communication<--- Enterprise demand	0.991	0.037	26.880	*_0P**	0.875
Expertise<--- Enterprise demand	0.949	0.039	24.585	***	0.832
Teamwork<--- Enterprise demand	0.983	0.038	25.868	***	0.857
Professional capacity<--- Employability	1.000				0.813
Interpersonal skills<--- Employability	1.172	0.040	29.348	***	0.968
Self-development capacities<--- Employability	1.139	0.041	27.579	***	0.935
Emotional adjustment ability<--- Employability	1.160	0.040	29.2700	***	0.967

As can be seen from Table 5-9 above, the standardized coefficient of the path “Employability<--- Enterprise demand” is 1.004, C.R value is 23.381>2.58, and the path coefficient is significant at the level of 0.001, which confirms hypothesis H.

6. RESEARCH CONCLUSION

This study focuses on the influence mechanism of enterprise demand on employability, makes assumptions on enterprise demand and employability, designs a questionnaire with reference to the existing maturity scale, collects sample data. The empirical analysis of the sample data of 298 valid questionnaires mainly leads to the following conclusions.

According to the results of correlation analysis, the correlation coefficient between employability and enterprise demand is positive, and there is a significant positive correlation among the variables, which preliminarily confirms the hypotheses proposed above. The standardized regression coefficient of the path “Employability<--- Enterprise demand” is 1.004, C.R value is 23.381>2.58, and the path coefficient is significant at the level of 0.001, so hypothesis H is further verified by sample data.

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